

Entropy and the Second law of Thermodynamics from the Perspective of Correlations between Subsystems

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The interpretation of entropy and its relationship to irreversibility is still a key issue in statistical mechanics. One longstanding difficulty is understanding how macroscopic irreversibility emerges from dynamical laws that are invariant under time reversal. Recent studies have emphasized the importance of correlations, as measured by mutual information, in describing entropy production, especially in the context of system-environment interactions. In this study, we expand on this concept by examining how correlations evolve within a composite system. Within an information-theoretic framework, the entropy of a composite system can be expressed in terms of the entropies of its subsystems and their mutual information. This relationship suggests that growth in correlations could be pivotal in approaching equilibrium. To investigate this idea, we introduce a numerical model consisting of two initially uncorrelated sets of interacting variables and analyze how their mutual information evolves. Starting from zero, it increases. For sufficiently large systems, the mutual information converges to a stationary value that aligns with the microcanonical Boltzmann–Planck formula. These results support interpreting the second law of thermodynamics in terms of the growth of correlations between subsystems. They also provide insight into the microscopic origin of irreversibility and related fundamental questions.

1. Introduction

By the end of the nineteenth century, the first and second laws of thermodynamics had become an extraordinarily effective framework for designing engines, power plants, and refrigeration systems.

Despite this empirical success, physicists continue to debate the fundamental meaning of entropy, the microscopic origins of irreversibility, and whether the second law is a fundamental law of nature or a statistical tendency arising from additional assumptions. A central question is how macroscopic irreversibility emerges from the fundamental laws of classical and quantum mechanics, which are time-reversal invariant (reversibility paradox).

In 1872, Ludwig Boltzmann made the first attempt to explain the evolution of a gas composed of atoms interacting through collisions. His work was based on the molecular chaos hypothesis (Stosszahlansatz), which assumes that colliding particles are statistically independent [1]. However, collisions generate statistical correlations between particle variables and two atoms that have collided are correlated.

In 1876, Josef Loschmidt pointed out that reversing particle velocities should, in principle, return the system to its initial low-entropy state due to time-reversal symmetry [2]. However, since the two atoms involved in the time-reversal process resulted from a collision, their variables are related. This highlights a limitation of the molecular chaos hypothesis when applied to reversed dynamics. In this context, correlations play a central role in developing a consistent interpretation of entropy and the second law. The correlation expression we use is provided by information theory [3].

Since 2008, several studies have examined the role of correlations in the analysis of irreversibility, including works by Li [4,5], Zhang [6], Massimiliano Esposito and collaborators [7], and Fedus [8].

In particular, Ref. [5], based on a Markovian master equation, shows that entropy production can be interpreted in terms of the growth of system–environment correlations, stating that “...the second law statement that the irreversible entropy keeps increasing ... can be also equivalently understood as, the correlation between the system and its environment, as measured by the mutual information, always keeps increasing until they get the equilibrium. »

Arieh Ben-Naim [9] emphasized the physical origin of these correlations, noting that “*the interactions between the particles produce correlations, which [...] can be cast in the form of mutual information between the particles.*”

Interactions play a central role in the dynamical evolution of physical systems. In the present work, no specific interaction potential is assumed; instead, the analysis relies on general properties such as

Liouville's theorem, which applies in both classical and quantum contexts. Within this framework, interactions can give rise to the development of correlations and are associated with entropy production. Irreversible phenomena are further characterized by the tendency of the distribution function to approach a unique equilibrium distribution, largely independent of initial conditions. A consistent description of irreversibility should account for both the increase of entropy and this convergence toward equilibrium.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the relevant definitions of correlation. Section 3 presents the numerical model and simulation results. The model is used to examine whether interpreting the second law in terms of correlation growth provides a consistent description of irreversible behaviors. Section 4 discusses the implications for both the model and physical systems. Section 5 examines the conceptual foundations of entropy and irreversibility as they can be figured out from the results of the numerical model. Section 6 outlines implications for the interpretation and teaching of thermodynamics. Appendix A shows how Clausius's relation $dS=dE/T$ can be derived from an information-theoretic definition of entropy (the SMI). Appendix B provides implementation details for the numerical model. Appendix C discusses the role of mixing properties in the evolution of the system and their connection to irreversibility.

2. Defining correlations between either random variables or sets of variables

2.1. Defining correlations between random variables

The definition of correlation is based on the idea that variables X and Y are correlated if the values of variable X provide an indication of the values of Y (and vice versa). They are uncorrelated if this is not the case. If P_x is a probability function of the random variable X , we know that the amount of information needed to determine event X is given by $SMI[P_x]$ which stands for "Shannon Measure of Information": $SMI[P_x] = -\sum P_x \log P_x$. The same holds true for events Y and events (X, Y) .

If X and Y are independent, then the information needed to determine the event (X, Y) is the sum of the information needed to separately determine X and Y , i.e., $SMI[P_{XY}] = SMI[P_x] + SMI[P_y]$. This is a mathematical consequence of the fact that $P(X, Y) = P(X).P(Y)$ when X and Y are independent.

Conversely, if knowing X provides information about Y , then $SMI[P_x] + SMI[P_y]$ accounts for this amount of information twice. Consequently, this sum is greater than $SMI(X, Y)$. This excess information is called mutual information and is denoted $MI(X, Y)$:

$$MI(X, Y) = SMI[P_x] + SMI[P_y] - SMI[P_{XY}] \quad (1)$$

It is necessarily positive or zero, since only two cases are possible: either X provides information about Y , or it does not. The positivity of MI is also mathematically verified:

$$MI(X, Y) = -\sum_x P_x \cdot \log[P_x] - \sum_y P_y \cdot \log[P_y] + \sum_{xy} P_{xy} \cdot \log[P_{xy}] = \sum_{xy} P_{xy} \cdot \log \left[\frac{P_{xy}}{P_x P_y} \right] \equiv D(P_{xy} \| P_x P_y) \quad (2)$$

Since the Kullback-Leibler divergence $D(P_{xy} \| P_x P_y)$ is nonnegative, it follows that mutual information, $MI(X, Y)$, is also nonnegative. Furthermore, $MI(X, Y)$ is zero if and only if the variables are independent. $MI(X, Y)$ is the more appropriate way to measure the strength of the relationship, i.e., the correlation, between X and Y .

2.2. Correlation Measure Between Two Sets of Variables A and B

Similarly, the correlation between particles of systems A and particles of systems B can be measured by the mutual information defined for the two sets of variables A and B using classical phase space densities ρ_A , ρ_B , and $\rho_{A\&B}$ [10] :

$$MI = \{SMI[\rho_A] + SMI[\rho_B]\} - SMI[\rho_{A\&B}] \quad (3)$$

where SMI stands for Shannon Measures of Information :

$$SMI[\rho(\vec{Q}, \vec{P})] = - \int \rho(\vec{Q}, \vec{P}) \ln \rho(\vec{Q}, \vec{P}) d\vec{Q}d\vec{P} \quad (4)$$

and where \vec{Q} and \vec{P} are generalized phase space coordinates. Any variation of mutual information ΔMI may be written as a Kullback-Leibler divergence $D(\rho_{A\&B} \| \rho_A \rho_B)$. Since any Kullback-Leibler divergence is

nonnegative, any state coming from an uncorrelated state ($MI=0$) must have a higher correlation measure:

$$\Delta MI = MI^{final} - MI^{initial} \geq 0 \quad (5)$$

According to Liouville's theorem, $SMI[\rho_{A\&B}]$ remains constant in Eq. (3). Consequently, any variation in MI implies the same variation in $SMI[\rho_A] + SMI[\rho_B]$.

$$\Delta MI = MI^{final} - MI^{initial} = \{SMI[\rho_A] + SMI[\rho_B]\}^{final} - \{SMI[\rho_A] + SMI[\rho_B]\}^{initial} \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

This property applies, for instance, for to subsystems A and B that have not yet interacted. At that moment, the mutual information is zero and the variation of mutual information (MI) between that time and any later time is positive. Except for a multiplicative constant, this inequality is identical to Planck's formulation of the second law of thermodynamics [11]: *"Every physical and chemical process in nature proceeds in such a way that the sum of the entropies of all bodies involved increases. In the limit, i.e., for reversible processes, this sum remains unchanged."*

According to this, the second law can be interpreted as stating that the correlation between systems A and B increases as soon as their particles interact. From this perspective, irreversibility reflects an increase in correlations regardless of the type of interaction.

3. The Toy model for the analysis of increasing correlations between two subsystems

3.1. Introduction

The model consists of two sets, A and B, of N_A and N_B random variables, respectively. The hyperspace which is built on the set of all variables will still be called phase space, as in mechanics. The coordinates of a point in phase space determine the system's microstate at a given moment. At a later time, the point will occupy a different position that corresponds to a different microstate. The system's evolution is based on the trajectory of its representative point in phase space. This trajectory is defined by a succession of microstates, each of which is distinguished by a unique numerical identifier.

Fig. 1 a) Here is one of the many possible directed closed chains in a contingency table for three discrete variables and three categories. The length of the chain is $n_{categories}^{N_{variables}} = 3^3 = 27$.
b) The ordered sequence of microstates.

This approach resembles classical models such as Kac rings, Ehrenfest urns, and Markov processes. However, it does not assume coarse-graining or transition probabilities that do not satisfy the detailed balance condition.

This model only assumes that the representative point of the system passes through all microstates with an appropriate energy-entropy value and meets all other possible criteria, if any. In particular, I am thinking of the Pauli exclusion principle.

In thermodynamic systems, the laws of mechanics and the intermolecular potential determine the sequence of microstates traversed by the system's representative point. In this model, the chain is directly given in phase space by a simple, deterministic algorithm. At each stage, the correlation between the subsets will be calculated, and the results are enlightening.

3.2. A statistical model

Three multivariate distribution functions — P_A , P_B and $P_{A\&B}$ — are used to describe both subsystems and the global system. The initial values of the P_A and P_B distributions are chosen at random. The initial lack of correlation between the two subsystems implies that the probability distribution for all the variables is $P_{A\&B} = P_A P_B$.

If there is a probability P that the representative point will be at a certain location at a given time, and if the system must transfer to a different location at the next instant, then the probability of being at that location at that time is also P . Thus, as the representative point displaces along this chain, its probability of presence shifts as well. Therefore, at each step, all the $P_{A\&B}$ probability values shift one step forward along the chain of microstates. Because an accumulation of points is impossible, the chain is closed and cyclically accommodates the system's representative point and its probability.

3.3. Variables used for the Toy Model

The program begins with the random generation of the two distribution functions, P_A and P_B , which have $N_A = 2$ and $N_B = 3$ as their default values, respectively. For simplicity, all variables have the same number of categories which is defined at the beginning of the program. Each microstate is a set of N_{var} values corresponding to the N_{var} variables.

The maximum number of microstates is $MaxSIZE = n_{categories}^{N_{var}}$. The sequence of the microstates visited by the system's representative point in phase space forms a chain of length $chainSIZE$ where $chainSIZE \leq MaxSIZE$. Most of the time, $chainSIZE$ is set to $MaxSIZE$. More details about programming the toy model can be found in Appendix D.

3.4. Two types of microstate chains

- All the possible microstate chain going through all microstates are the permutations of the integers $1, 2, \dots, CHAINsize$ completed by a return from the last element to the first one. For example, an "ordinary" chain can be constructed by means of arithmetic progressions. In a series constructed this way, there are strong links between successive values. This can be seen through high autocorrelation measures and low global mixing index (M) values (see Appendix C).
- On the other hand, microstate chains with a vanishing autocorrelation measure can be obtained as follows: First, an algorithm like the Arnold Cat Map is used to construct a series of numbers ranging from 0 to 1. The integer part of the product of each of these numbers by $MaxSize$ yields a value between 1 and $MaxSize$. This value corresponds to one of the possible microstates. If each value is selected only once, this provides the microstate chain that governs the system's evolution. Finally, to create a closed chain of microstates, the last element is connected to the first one. The corresponding algorithm is given in Appendix B.

3.5. Evolution of the toy model

Equation (5) shows that the mutual information, $MI(A, B)$, is positive almost everywhere except when $P_{A\&B} = P_A \times P_B$, at which point it vanishes.

All elements of $P_{A\&B}$ are cyclically shifted on the microstate chain. The two marginal distributions (P_A and P_B) as well as the sum of the two corresponding SMI's are recalculated and the graph of the sum is displayed as the number of steps increases. Since the $P_{A\&B}$ distribution returns to its original value after $chainSIZE$ units of time, we expect the graph to have a period of $chainSIZE$.

The results stem from a microstate chain that occupied the entire available phase space (chainSIZE = MaxSIZE). The figures below show graphs of the sum of the two SMIs, calculated for both a mixing and a non-mixing chain. Thus, the difference between the two cases is clear.

3.6. Numerical and graphical outcomes

When working with two- and three-variable distributions of variables with two categories each, the total number of microstates is 2^5 or 32. If the dynamical chain of microstates passes through all possible microstates, then the period is equal to the length of the chain. In this case, the period is 32, as can be verified in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Evolution of $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$ over two periods, for $N_A=2$, $N_B=3$, and two categories.

After passing through all 32 states, the system returns to its initial state. Therefore, the graph has a period of 32. This return to the initial state is comparable to the Poincaré recurrence period. Outside of these points, the sum of the two SMIs is always greater than the initial value calculated for independent variables.

When the N_A and N_B values are low and the number of variable categories is small, the sum of the two SMIs fluctuates greatly.

Figure 3 Evolution of $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$ for five variables with two categories over one period. The blue line shows the mean value over 1,000 trials.

When the trial is repeated 1,000 times, these fluctuations tend to disappear, though the beginning and end of the curve remain. These parts of the graph are unaffected by random effects. The return to the initial value

is a common characteristic of all cases. The plateau value is close to the value $\log_2[2^{(3+2)}]$, which corresponds to the SMI for a uniform distribution of five variables with two categories. For variables with three categories, less significant fluctuations are observed. If the chain passes through all microstates, for five variables, the period is $3^5 = 243$.

Fig. 4 Evolution of $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$ and the A-B correlation, for variables with three categories.

The horizontal red line at a height of $\log_2(3^5)$ shows the SMI value of the uniform five-variable distribution in which all terms are equal to $1/3^5$.

Since $SMI[P_{A\&B}]$ is the sum of all chain rings and since all $P_{A\&B}$ values only slide on this chain, $SMI[P_{A\&B}]$ remains constant, as shown by the horizontal green line in Figure 4.

The sum of the SMIs of P_A and P_B varies between the limits of the two horizontal lines.

$$SMI[P_{A\&B}^{initial}] \leq SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B] \leq SMI[P_{A\&B}^{uniform}] = \log_2(n^5) \quad (7)$$

The red arrow in Fig. 5 shows the value of the mutual information $MI = SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B] - SMI[P_{A\&B}]$ i.e., the correlation between the two subsystems.

Figure 5: Evolution of $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$ for Two-Category Variables with a period of 2^5

At any point on the graph, the sum of the green and red vectors is equal to the length of the black segment. Once again, the uncorrelated term, $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$, and the correlated term, $SMI[P_{A\&B}]$, have equal growth rates.

Sum of the SMI for the 2- & 3-variable distributions (4 categories per variable)

Figure 6: Evolution of $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$ over two periods for five variables with four categories, in brown from a mixing transformation and in green from a non-mixing transformation based on arithmetic progressions.

Sum of the SMI for the 2- & 3-variable distributions 39 categories per variable

Figure 7: Evolution from a mixing transformation of $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$ over a short fraction of a period for five variables with thirty-nine categories, in brown.

As N_{var} , the number of variables, and categories increase, the numerical experiments described above show that the fluctuations become imperceptible and the difference between the plateau value and the high limit value $(N_A + N_B) \log_2(n_{categories})$ becomes negligible.

3.7. Plateau value versus the number of categories

The plateau values for $N_{var} = 2+3$ and an increasing number of categories N , are reported in the following table.

$N = 2$	$N = 3$	$N = 4$	$N = 5$	$N = 6$	$N = 7$	$N = 8$	$N = 9$	$N = 10$	$N = 15$	$N = 20$	$N = 25$
0,9592	0,99414	0,99641	0,99736	0,99845	0,99904	0,99938	0,99951	0,99963	0,99986	0,99992	0,99996

Moreover, for a large number of categories, the sum of the two SMIs nearly always has the same profile: a steep growth phase after the first interaction, followed by a plateau phase of length equal to $(n_{categories}^{(N_A + N_B)} - 1)$, before returning to the initial value. This pattern repeats.

3.8. Asymptotic behavior of $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$ for large number of variables

When the number of categories is 2 and the number of variables (N_{var}) increases, the sum of $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$ approaches $SMI [P_{A\&B}^{uniform}]$.

Total number of variables :	Nvar=5	Nvar=6	Nvar=7	Nvar=8	Nvar=9	Nvar=10	Nvar=11
$\frac{SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]}{SMI[P_{A\&B}]}$	0.95917	0.97823	0.98268	0.98277	0.98556	0.98759	0.98836

As the number of categories and variables increases, the sum of $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$ approaches the value $SMI[P_{A\&B}^{uniform}]$.

For an evolution law with mixing properties, we observe the second characteristic property of irreversible behavior; that is, an increase in the sum of the two marginal SMIs approaches the total system SMI value corresponding to a uniform distribution.

3.9. Two fundamental formulas

The numerical simulations performed lead to the assumption of the existence of two mathematical laws that could be formally demonstrated:

$$\lim_{N_{variables} \rightarrow \infty} \left[\lim_{n_{categories} \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \frac{SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]}{N_{variables} \times \log_2(n_{categories})} \right\} \right] = 1 \quad (8)$$

$$\lim_{n_{categories} \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \frac{SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]}{N_{variables} \times \log_2(n_{categories})} \right\} = 1 \quad (9)$$

Note that these two laws only hold true if the algorithm generating the chain of microstates in phase space meets the mixing property. As can be seen in Appendix C, the ratio of the sum of the two marginal SMIs to the total system SMI value corresponding to a uniform distribution tends not to 1, but to a value that decreases alongside the global mixing coefficient.

3.10. Interpretation of the results for high values of the number of categories and variables

Consider the $SMI[P_A] + SMI[P_B]$, measurements taken before and after interactions occurred, i.e., at the initial time or plateau stage. The graph's period is notably high, possibly reaching $(n_{categories})^{N_{variables}}$ unit time.

For a substantial number of categories and variables, a measurement taken within a finite amount of time is highly likely to yield a plateau value approaching $\log_2(n_{categories}^{N_{variables}})$.

We have always considered that the chain length (CHAINSsize) is equal to 100% of the maximum size (MAXsize = $n_{categories}^{N_{variables}}$). Of course, a lower percentage can be chosen. This can be achieved by stopping the chain generation procedure when the chain size reaches the expected value. We can expect that the microstates are still chosen uniformly throughout the space from 0 to MAXsize, without favoring any particular area of phase space. Formulas (8) and (9) are still valid but the tendency is slower.

3.11. Conclusions drawn from the numerical simulation applied to macroscopic systems

Macroscopic systems have a tremendous number of categories and variables. When a large number of variables and/or categories are considered and for a mixing state chain, the model yields two significant results that fully align with the second law: [13]

- ***The sum of the SMIs corresponding to P_A and P_B of two subsystems increases from the initial time, before the subsystems interacted, until a later time.***
- ***The maximum value of this sum is equal to the SMI of a single system with uniform probability distribution for all variables. This is usually called the microcanonical equilibrium distribution, in which all probability values are equal to $1/\Omega$, where $\Omega = n_{categories}^{N_{variables}}$.***

Moreover, we can expect to return to the initial time after a lapse of time of the order of $n_{categories}^{N_{variable}}$, i.e., after a time exceeding the duration of any human observation. Equivalently, we can say that the probability of observing such an event is vanishingly small, on the order of $1/n_{categories}^{N_{variable}}$.

For macroscopic systems, we should use entropy instead of SMIs. The two quantities differ only by a factor k_B , the Boltzmann factor, so the previous two properties also hold for entropy. Remember that variations of thermodynamic entropy and information-theoretic SMI are equivalent for equilibrium systems. See Appendix A.

Two main properties

- **The sum of the entropies of the two subsystems increases from the initial time, before the subsystems interacted, until a later time.**
- **The maximum value of the sum of the entropies of the two interacting subsystems is equal to the entropy of the global system evaluated using the uniform microcanonical equilibrium distribution, in which all probability values are equal to $1/\Omega$. Ω is the number of all possible microstates in phase space compatible with the system's volume, number of particles, and energy.**

The entropy corresponding to this distribution is given by the Boltzmann formula:

$$S^{\text{equilibrium}} = k_B \ln(\Omega) \quad (10)$$

This numerical model reveals that these two properties are valid only if the following conditions are met:

- The number of variables and/or categories is sufficiently high.
- The chain of microstates is given by a series of numbers that are independent of each other (see Appendix C).

For thermodynamic systems, the first condition is not problematic. Moreover, Sinai's theorem [12] suggests that most Hamiltonians of physical systems result in a mixing flux in phase space.

4 Conclusions

The two conditions necessary for observing an irreversible behavior are:

- The law of the evolution of the system in phase space possesses mixing properties.
- The number of particles must be high.

The following points of departure from standard theory can be identified:

- The correlation between parts A and B of a system is defined by equation (1) and exhibits the same growth rate as $\text{SMI}[\rho^{(A)}] + \text{SMI}[\rho^{(B)}]$ because $\text{SMI}[\rho^{(A\&B)}]$ is constant. Thus, the second law captures the correlation increase in between the two subsystems. This lends intuitive meaning to the second law, suggesting that correlations between sets of particles are fundamental to irreversibility.
- The measure of correlation involves several SMIs. This explains how the expression of the SMI of information theory appears in a theory of heat.
- Since mutual dependence between variables stems from particle interactions, the causality principle tells us that correlation appears after interactions occur. If entropy can be associated with correlation between subsystems, then it explains why the entropy variation has the same sign as the corresponding variation of time.
- The usual interpretation of the second law is linked to the idea of a preferred time direction, which is considered an intrinsic property of nature. The fact that irreversible properties also appear in the toy model without invoking any special property shows that assuming this property is unnecessary.
- The irreversibility of a transformation involving several interacting bodies can be described by an increase in the sum of the entropies of the different parts. Conversely, the Gibbs entropy (or global SMI) remains constant due to the reversibility of the laws of mechanics, and there is **no paradox of reversibility** in this context.

- The reduced model shows that the tendency to the uniform microcanonical equilibrium distribution is exact only at the asymptotic limit of the number of particles or categories. However, the uniform microcanonical equilibrium distribution is also a very good approximation from a number of variables as low as a few dozens.

The information-theoretic definition of correlations between interacting subsystems provides an intuitive and precise understanding of the second law. Using Planck's formulation of the second law of thermodynamics instead of Clausius's yields a version of thermodynamics that is free of paradoxes.

- Correlations between sets of particles play an essential role in explaining how irreversibility is compatible with the Liouville theorem. Similarly, when working with individual particles, the uncorrelated and correlated parts of a global SMI can be separated. Since 2010, several publications have concluded that these two parts increase at equal rates for both quantum [4-8] and classical [14] systems¹.

The essential role played by correlations also appears in our previous publication [15], showing that, when a system appears irreversible based on lowest-order distribution functions, correlations pertaining to higher-order distribution functions conserve the system's global information. These higher-order effects are barely detectable, effectively hiding the reversible aspects. In this view, irreversibility appears to be a consequence of incomplete observation, rather than a fundamental property of matter.

In the following section, we examine which reason could have led Clausius to not express the second law in terms of the sum of two marginal SMIs, as Planck did. Planck's formulation is more factual and closer to the interpretation in terms of correlations.

5 Historical aspects

The initial property listed in Section 3, which relates to increasing the sum of the two SMIs, is purely qualitative. Though it may seem insignificant, its impact ultimately proved essential. It enables predictions about the evolution of the two subsystems. These predictions are made by comparing initial and final entropy values. In the mid-1800s, Rudolf Clausius studied systems composed of subsystems, such as a heat source and a cylinder filled with gas. He observed that these subsystems could be assigned a "numerical value" and that the sum of these values for the subsystems at two different times could only increase. To render this property suitable for exploitation, Clausius developed a method for calculating the entropy of each subsystem, termed the "calorimetric method." This method is based on a formula that provides the change in entropy of a body in thermodynamic equilibrium at an absolute temperature (T) when it receives a quantity of heat (dE).

$$dS = dE/T \quad (11)$$

Clausius managed to derive this equation from the transformation of a piece of gas operating under the conditions envisioned by Sadi Carnot to produce the maximum amount of mechanical work from a given amount of heat.

Nowadays, we can demonstrate (see Appendix A) that Eq. (11) can be derived from the Gibbs entropy formula (4) when applied to a body that is in an equilibrium state and receives a small amount of heat dE. However, this does not mean that the Gibbs entropy of a system composed of two interacting subsystems increases until equilibrium is reached. Rather, it indicates that, before any interaction, the entropy of each component of a thermodynamic system that is in an equilibrium state, is given by the value of the corresponding Gibbs entropy.

By the mid-19th century, the conservation laws of momentum and energy were widely accepted for systems of material points. In this frame of reference, each quantity is expressed as the sum of momenta

¹ Up to a constant, the uncorrelated part of the global SMI can be identified with the SMI of the single-particle distribution function, $f(\vec{q}, \vec{p})$. Conversely, up to a constant, the measure of the correlation that exists between the variables of particles 1 and 2 involves the two-particle distribution function $f(\vec{q}_1, \vec{p}_1, \vec{q}_2, \vec{p}_2)$. This measure is positive and it vanishes only when $f(\vec{q}_1, \vec{p}_1, \vec{q}_2, \vec{p}_2) = f(\vec{q}_1, \vec{p}_1) \times f(\vec{q}_2, \vec{p}_2)$.

or energies. This may explain why Clausius formulated the rule governing thermodynamic systems by replacing “the sum of the components' entropies” with “the global system's entropy” or “the entropy of the world”. [13]

- First law: **Die Energie der Welt ist constant. (The energy of the world is constant).**
- Second law: **Die Entropie der Welt strebt einem Maximum zu. (The entropy of the world strives to a maximum).**

As pointed out by Ben-Naim, [9] “Clearly, Clausius’ “definition” [of entropy] cannot be applied to the entire universe. First, because the universe is not a welldefined, thermodynamic system at constant temperature for which the quantity dQ/T may be applied.”

Clausius’ formulation of the second law has adverse consequences.

It leads to the tendency to analyze irreversibility within the framework of a single system. This implies that the initial state is necessarily out of equilibrium, making it unclear whether values calculated by the equilibrium calorimetric method can be used.

- By using the expression "entropy of the world" to designate the sum of the entropies of different subsystems, and without stating it, Clausius endorsed the principle of additivity of entropies:

$$SMI[\rho^{(A\&B)}] = SMI[\rho^{(A)}] + SMI[\rho^{(B)}] \quad (12)$$

This principle is necessary to transform the theoretical second law into what is observed: an increase in the sum of two numerical values. This principle seems to be as essential as the second law of thermodynamics itself because it is used whenever the latter is applied.

- In actual applications, the second law of thermodynamics is always used in the form stated by Planck (1897) [11], in which each subsystem is in equilibrium: “Every physical and chemical process in nature proceeds in such a way that the sum of the entropies of all bodies involved increases. In the limit, i.e., for reversible processes, this sum remains unchanged.”

Planck’s and Clausius’ formulations are only equivalent if the entropy of the thermodynamic system is the sum of the entropies of its subsystems. As several 20th-century authors have pointed out, this assertion is incorrect after interactions have occurred or in cases of long-range interactions.

- Once it was proven that the entropy given by Eq. (4) is constant by means of the Liouville theorem, it was realized that "entropy" could not increase and remain constant at the same time ("paradox of irreversibility"). The paradox is avoided if the increasing quantity is considered to be $SMI[\rho^{(A)}] + SMI[\rho^{(B)}]$, not $SMI[\rho^{(A\&B)}]$.
- There are several reasons to reject the entropy additivity principle. From Eq. (3) and the positivity of $M^{(A,B)}$, it follows that entropy is subadditive, not additive, like $SMI[\rho^{(A\&B)}]$.
- Another argument against the additivity of entropy arises from the Boltzmann-Planck entropy expression. This expression states that the entropy of system A&B is the logarithm of the total number of microstates of the global system $\Omega_{A\&B}(E_A, E_B)$. However, this number is only the product of $\Omega_A(E_A)$ and $\Omega_B(E_B)$ if subsystems A and B are independent. Otherwise, only the total energy E is fixed, and the entropy of the combined system is no longer the sum of the separate entropies. The total number of accessible microstates can be evaluated as a sum over all possible energy distributions, i.e., the convolution integral $\int_0^E \Omega_A(E_A) \Omega_B(E - E_A) dE_A$.

6 Possible implications for the conceptual foundations and teaching of thermodynamics

Although modifying established practices is challenging, using Planck's formulation of the second law of thermodynamics as a pedagogical approach would make it easier for students and scientists to understand the fundamental concept of thermodynamics and avoid paradoxes.

Planck's formulation relates to the sum of the subsystem entropies. Consequently, it is not contradicted by the invariance of total system entropy. The paradox of reversibility no longer exists, so we can disregard the principle of additivity of entropy, which has become useless.

Planck's approach also aligns with the correlation-based interpretation of the second law of thermodynamics. The correlation between subsystems A and B is given by $MI^{(A&B)} = SMI[\rho^{(A)}] + SMI[\rho^{(B)}] - SMI[\rho^{(A&B)}]$. Since $SMI[\rho^{(A&B)}]$ is constant (Liouville's theorem), $MI^{(A&B)}$ has the same growth rate as the sum $SMI[\rho^{(A)}] + SMI[\rho^{(B)}]$. Consequently, the second law of thermodynamics can be rewritten as follows: ***"Every physical and chemical process in nature proceeds in such a way that there is an increase in the measure of correlations between all the variables of the bodies involved in the process in one way or another."***

This statement does not focus on each subsystem separately, but rather on all of them together, which would have been regarded as a marked improvement by Clausius.

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## Appendix A

### Proof of the theoretical basis for the Calorimetric Method

This Appendix establishes a direct connection between the information theoretical SMI and the Clausius' formula:

$$dS = dE/T \quad (\text{A.1})$$

First, it should be noted that a table of values of entropy value of a body versus its energies would not allow us to attribute an entropy value to that body because we are unable to determine a body's energy. However, the temperature of a system is directly related to the average energy of the system's molecules, and temperature can be measured. Therefore, the objective is to calculate the entropy values of a system from its known parameters T, V, and N.

We will start with the **Gibbs entropy** formula (4). We will not apply it with the equilibrium uniform distribution,  $1/\Omega$ , substituted for  $\rho$ , as this is only valid for a system with a given energy, volume, and number of particles. Instead, we will use the equilibrium Maxwell-Boltzmann canonical distribution.

$$\rho_{(\vec{Q}, \vec{P})}^{\text{eq}} = \frac{e^{-H(\vec{Q}, \vec{P})/kT}}{Z} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

In this formula,  $H(\vec{Q}, \vec{P})$  is the system's Hamiltonian and Z is the normalization factor

$$Z = \int e^{-\frac{H(\vec{Q}, \vec{P})}{k_B T}} d\vec{Q} d\vec{P} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The integral is taken over the full phase space. Plugging  $\rho^{\text{eq}}(q,p)$  into the entropy expression (1) and using the definition of internal energy as a mean value of the Hamiltonian:

$$E = \langle H \rangle = \int \rho(\vec{Q}, \vec{P}) H(\vec{Q}, \vec{P}) d\vec{Q} d\vec{P} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

gives:

$$S = E/T + k_B \ln Z \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Now let us compute the elementary change in entropy: dS corresponding to an elementary change in energy dE, assuming that the volume is constant (so, Z is only a function of T):

$$dS = dE/T - (E/T^2)dT + k_B d \ln Z \quad (\text{A.6})$$

The last term can be simplified by using the definition of Z:

$$\frac{d \ln Z}{dT} = \frac{\int e^{-\frac{H(\vec{Q}, \vec{P})}{k_B T}} \frac{H(\vec{Q}, \vec{P})}{k_B T^2} d\vec{Q} d\vec{P}}{Z} = \frac{1}{k_B T^2} \int \rho(\vec{Q}, \vec{P}) H(\vec{Q}, \vec{P}) d\vec{Q} d\vec{P} = \frac{E}{k_B T^2} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Finally:

$$dS = dE/T \quad (\text{A.8})$$

This formula demonstrates the equivalence between the calorimetric and information-theoretic definitions of entropy. However, it should be noted that this only applies to systems in equilibrium and not to systems on the verge of transformation.

Despite its small size, this formula has had a significant impact on science. It offered the first practical method for evaluating entropy variation in any system between two different states using available experimental data, such as the specific heat of gases at constant pressure and the latent heat of phase changes.

## Appendix B

## Programming the toy model

### Two possible types of the overall distribution function

There are two possible parameterizations for manipulating the distribution function. When five variables are grouped into sets of three and two variables, the overall probability distribution can be either the five-variable  $P_{ijklm}$  distribution or the synthetic distribution  $P(r)$ , where  $r = iN^4 + jN^3 + kN^2 + N + m$ , and  $N$  is the number of categories for each variable.

If the variables of a probability distribution are grouped into two nonempty subsets, the corresponding marginal distributions are obtained by summing the overall distribution. Using the five-variable  $P_{ijklm}$  distribution requires rewriting the entire code to increase the number of nested summations over  $P_{ijklm}$  when upgrading the code for a higher number of variables. In contrast, when the  $P(r)$  parameterization is used, for one of the marginal distributions, only the upper bound of the summation over the single variable  $r$  needs to be updated.

### Equivalence of the two parameterizations for calculating the marginal probabilities in the case $nvar=2+3$ , and $N=2$

The marginal probability  $P_{ij\dots}$ , for example, is obtained by summing eight values of  $P_{ijklm}$  over all values of  $k$ ,  $l$ , and  $m$ . When the  $P_{ab}(r)$  parameterization is used, the values to be summed are  $P(r)$  with specific values. For  $P_{\dots klm}$ , the specific values of  $r$  are 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7. These values are all listed in Column 2 of Table A and can be generated using the two pieces of code in Column 3.

Table A The arguments of  $P_{ab}(r)$  involved in the sums giving the 12 marginal probabilities (for  $nvar=2+3$ ;  $N=2$ )

| Marginal probabilities<br>$P_{\dots klm}$ & $P_{ij\dots}$ | The values of $r$ in $P_{ab}(r)$ that are to be summed to obtain the marginal probabilities given in the first column in terms of the basic representation. | VBA code that builds the series of $r$ values given in column 2                                                                              |
|-----------------------------------------------------------|-------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|----------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|
| $P_{00klm}$                                               | 0 , 1 , 2 , 3 , 4 , 5 , 6 , 7                                                                                                                               | For $r = 0$ to $N^2 * N^3 - 1$<br>DISPLAY " r = " & r<br>If $(r + 1) / N^3 = (r + 1) \setminus N^3$ Then DISPLAY vbCrLf<br>Next r            |
| $P_{01klm}$                                               | 8 , 9 , 10 , 11 , 12 , 13 , 14 , 15                                                                                                                         |                                                                                                                                              |
| $P_{10klm}$                                               | 16 , 17 , 18 , 19 , 20 , 21 , 22 , 23                                                                                                                       |                                                                                                                                              |
| $P_{11klm}$                                               | 24 , 25 , 26 , 27 , 28 , 29 , 30 , 31                                                                                                                       |                                                                                                                                              |
| $P_{ij000}$                                               | 0 , 8 , 16 , 24                                                                                                                                             | For $i=0$ to $N^3$<br>$r = 0$<br>Do<br>DISPLAY "r= " & r + i<br>$r = r + N^3$<br>Loop Until $r >= N^2 * N^3 - 1$<br>DISPLAY vbCrLf<br>Next i |
| $P_{ij001}$                                               | 1 , 9 , 17 , 25                                                                                                                                             |                                                                                                                                              |
| $P_{ij010}$                                               | 2 , 10 , 18 , 26                                                                                                                                            |                                                                                                                                              |
| $P_{ij011}$                                               | 3 , 11 , 19 , 27                                                                                                                                            |                                                                                                                                              |
| $P_{ij100}$                                               | 4 , 12 , 20 , 28                                                                                                                                            |                                                                                                                                              |
| $P_{ij101}$                                               | 5 , 13 , 21 , 29                                                                                                                                            |                                                                                                                                              |
| $P_{ij110}$                                               | 6 , 14 , 22 , 30                                                                                                                                            |                                                                                                                                              |
| $P_{ij111}$                                               | 7 , 15 , 23 , 31                                                                                                                                            |                                                                                                                                              |

In the code,  $N$  denotes the number of categories, while 2 and 3 represent the number of variables considered in the two subsets, respectively. These two pieces of code can easily be upgraded to accommodate an increased number of variables.

### Constructing the microstate chain

The total number of microstates in phase space is  $(n_{\text{categories}})^{Nvar}$ . The number of microstates in the chain is  $chainSIZE \leq (n_{\text{categories}})^{Nvar}$ .

The main concern to create a set of integer values ranging from 0 to  $chainSIZE-1$  that are stored in a vector called "ORIGIN." Each value must appear once and only once. The first element is "0," and the last element is connected to the first one to close the chain.

For example, an oriented chain of four elements can be represented by the closed chain 0213 (meaning  $0 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 0$ ). In this case, the vector would be  $ORIGIN(0) = 3$ ,  $ORIGIN(3) = 1$ ,  $ORIGIN(1) = 2$ , and  $ORIGIN(2) = 0$ . There are  $3!$  different possible chains with 0 in the first position.

The most efficient way to obtain a permutation of a set of numbers with a low autocorrelation coefficient—or, equivalently, a high mixing index—is to start with an ordered sequence of those numbers. Then, the first number in the sequence is considered and exchanged with a number of a higher index. To select this index, one could use a random number generator or the generator provided by the Arnold cat transformation. Since the Arnold cat transformation is entirely deterministic, the chain of microstates constructed from it is also deterministic, as are the microstates resulting from Hamiltonian dynamics. This process is applied successively to each subsequent element.

Two ways to reduce the size of the chain: decreasing MaxSIZE or CHAINsize.

Conversely, decreasing the size of the chain stops the construction of the microstate chain before it reaches the maximum size. However, values from the entire available space are still possible, and the microstate chain's mixing property is preserved.

Algorithm for constructing the microstate chain:

- 1) Fill the ORIGIN vector,  $ORIGIN(i)$ , with successive integers from zero to  $N - 1$ .
- 2) Exchange  $ORIGIN(1)$  with an element located to the right which is determined by Arnold's cat map.
- 3) Repeat this operation for all following elements from 2 to  $N - 1$ .
- 4) Complete the resulting vector with two instructions to link the beginning and end of the string:  $ORIGIN(0) = N - 1$  and  $ORIGIN(N - 1) = 0$ .

#### 2D-Arnold's Cat Map

The two-dimensional Arnold transformation maps a point  $(x, y)$  in the set  $[0, 1]^2$  to a new point  $(x', y')$  by wrapping values modulo 1 to keep them on the torus, i.e., in the set  $[0, 1]^2$ . This transformation can be expressed in matrix notation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x' \\ y' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \text{ mod } 1 \quad (\text{B.1})$$



Figure B.1 Applying transformation (B.1) to all points in the square  $[0, 1]^2$ . First, this yields the parallelogram between points  $(0, 0)$  and  $(3, 2)$ . Next, the modulo operation moves the colored triangles back into the square  $[0, 1]^2$ .

## Appendix C Measure of the mixing level of the microstate chain and its consequences

The toy model shows that the two properties that lead to the second law of thermodynamics are not obtained if the microstate is short or exhibits regularities. This appendix addresses this issue.

Autocorrelation coefficient and the global mixing index

If you are given the first two or three digits of the sequence 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, you can expect the end of the pattern. Even if no obvious rule exists, there may be hidden links between the elements. For long series of digits, the autocorrelation coefficient and the global mixing index  $M$  can be used to measure the extent to which values separated by some lag are related. For a series  $x_i$  of length  $N$  with a mean  $\bar{x}$  and a variance  $\sigma$ , the autocorrelation coefficient is defined as:

$$\rho(\text{lag}) = \sum_{i=\text{lag}+1}^N \frac{(x_i - \bar{x})(x_{i-\text{lag}} - \bar{x})}{(N - \text{lag})\sigma^2}$$

The global mixing index is defined as follows:

$$M = 1 - \frac{1}{K} \sum_{\text{lag}=1}^K |\rho(\text{lag})|$$

A sequence with strong mixing has autocorrelation coefficients,  $\rho(\text{lag})$ , close to 0, and a global mixing index,  $M$ , close to 1.  $M$  close to 0 indicates poor mixing (strong memory).

Application to Microstate Chains

The algorithm given in Appendix B generates a series with a global mixing index close to 1 during the construction of the microstate chain.

We hypothesize that there is a link between the mixing level of the microstate chain and the maximum value reached by the sum of the SMIs of the two marginal distributions. To test this relationship, we require series with correlation indexes ranging from 0 to 1. One valuable method is to start with a series that has an index of 1 and progressively decrease the index by merging an increasing number of elements from the end of the series. For each constructed chain, we use the toy model to compute the maximum value of the sum of the SMIs of the two marginal distributions. The following figures illustrate the general trend, showing more fluctuations with a low number of categories.



The sum of the SMIs of the two marginal distributions versus the mixing characteristic of the transformation (N= 10)



The sum of the SMIs of the two marginal distributions versus the mixing characteristic of the transformation (N= 24)



Figure C.1,2,3 The relationship between the maximum mutual information value and the global mixing index for the numbers in the microstates chain governing the evolution of the two sets of variables with  $N_{\text{categories}} = 6, 10, \text{ and } 24$ , respectively.

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